

Validation of the FOPS Analysis of an Operator Cabin Through Physical Testing

Ali BEKTAŞ

Hidromek A.Ş., Ankara, 06935, Türkiye

Abstract

Falling-object Protective Structures (FOPS) are protective frameworks specifically developed in the construction and heavy machinery industry to ensure operator safety against hazardous objects that may fall from above. These systems are predominantly manufactured from steel frame structures. The working environments of operators often involve demanding and hazardous conditions. During such operations, heavy and potentially fatal objects such as rocks, trees, or construction materials may fall onto the operator cabin, posing a serious threat to life. To safeguard operator safety in these circumstances, FOPS standards have been established. In this context, structural analyses were conducted on the operator cabin of a HİDROMEK construction machine, with the objective of ensuring its successful performance in FOPS testing through pre-test inspections and verifications. Subsequently, the correlation between the physical test results and the numerical analyses was examined, thereby confirming the validation.

Keywords: DLV; Falling-object Protective Structures; FOPS; Structural Analysis

1. Introduction

During the production of an operator cabin, numerous factors must be taken into consideration. These include comfort, safety, compactness, and visibility convenience, among others. Among these, the FOPS safety requirement is one of the most critical aspects for the operator. In order for the cabin to meet the safety limitations defined by the standard, design-stage verifications must be performed so that the cabin becomes suitable for testing. Figure 1. illustrates an operator cabin prepared for testing along with the test setup. Initially, the operator cabin must be properly fixed to the ground. Any potential horizontal displacement of the cabin during the test may result in test failure. In the subsequent stage, a mass whose dimensions, weight, and drop height are defined by the standard is positioned accordingly. Within the cabin, a Deflection-Limiting Volume (DLV), dimensioned in compliance with the standard, is placed, after which the mass is released onto the cabin structure.

Figure 1. Test setup

After the completion of the test, the operator cabin must not come into contact with the Deflection-Limiting Volume (DLV) under any circumstances. Such contact may occur in cases of roof panel deformation, breaking of the roof sheet, or detachment of the cabin from its joints. If any contact with the DLV is observed, the test must be repeated. Another critical issue concerns the exact location where the standard-defined mass is to be dropped onto the cabin. The standard specifies that the mass should be released onto areas of the cabin roof that are structurally weaker, and not directly onto load-bearing regions such as the pillars. In cases where different materials and thicknesses are used on the upper surface of the DLV, each region must be subjected to testing. For each target point, the impact location is selected as close as possible to the center of gravity on the top horizontal surface of the DLV, while ensuring it does not overlap with the primary structural members at the uppermost section. An illustrative example is provided below.

Figure 2. Load drop zone

2. Materials and Methods

In this section, detailed information regarding the FOPS validation analysis conducted on the operator cabin of a Hidromek construction machine is presented. The physical test was validated using the Finite Element Method (FEM). Geometry simplifications and modifications for the analysis were performed using ANSYS SpaceClaim, while all meshing and pre-analysis preparations were carried out in MSC Apex. The modeling process was established using shell elements, and the finite element solution was executed through MSC Marc-Mentat.

Figure 3. FOPS analysis stage

The operator cabin used for validation consisted of two different materials, both of which are widely used structural steels. The mechanical properties of these materials are provided in the table below. Since the FOPS analysis includes both linear and nonlinear regions, the material characterization was based on tensile test data specifically obtained by our company.

Table 1. Material properties

Elasticity Modulus (GPa)	210
Poisson Ratio	0.3
Density(t/mm ³)	$7.85e^{-9}$

During the analysis, a DLV (Deflection-Limiting Volume) structure was mounted in accordance with the SIP (Seat Index Point) defined by the standard. Contact interactions were monitored throughout the analysis in order to obtain essential preliminary information required for the subsequent physical testing.

2.1. Finite Element Modeling

In this study, the dynamic behavior of the FOPS system was analyzed using the Finite Element Method (FEM) in order to evaluate its performance. The operator cabin, prepared in a CAD environment for analysis, was meshed within MSC Apex. The cabin was modeled using shell elements, consisting predominantly of Quad4 elements, with a smaller proportion of Tet3 elements. Due to the inherent complexity and challenging surface transitions of the cabin geometry, the exclusive use of Quad4 elements in such regions would result in low-quality mesh elements.

Figure 4. Element type

Since the FOPS analysis is a nonlinear type of analysis, solving it can be highly challenging. To avoid potential computational issues, both the element quality and the element count are of critical importance. Sharp corners must be captured using multiple refined elements to accurately represent the geometry. Otherwise, convergence difficulties or unrealistic results are highly probable.

An illustrative correction method is provided below. Elements highlighted in green are classified as high-quality according to the program's quality indicator, whereas elements highlighted in orange are considered poor. Examination of the orange elements reveals issues with their aspect ratio, which indicates that the skewness value deviates significantly from that of an ideal element.

Figure 5. Model with bad element quality(a) and model with good element quality

(a)

(b)

Figure 6. FOPS finite element model

2.2. Determination of Boundary Conditions

As shown below, the stress–strain curves for the two different materials used in the cabin structure are presented. To facilitate computational efficiency within the solver, a simplified linear approximation was adopted. Although attempts were made using a parabolic input curve, no significant differences in results were observed, while the solution time was substantially increased. Furthermore, in cases with parabolic inputs, convergence issues were encountered particularly during analysis steps involving large plastic deformations. Consequently, the material curves presented in the graphs below were selected for the FOPS analysis.

Figure 7. Plastic region definition for material 1 (left) and material 2 (right)

According to the standard, the FOPS analysis consists of two different levels, each defined by distinct mass and drop height parameters. Based on these specifications, the impact mass for the FOPS analysis was positioned above the operator

cabin. Since this is a dynamic analysis, computation times tend to be considerably long. When adapting the free-fall FOPS test into finite element analysis, releasing the mass from the full prescribed height would result in impractically long solution times. Therefore, the impact mass was placed very close to the cabin, with a clearance of approximately 1–2 mm being sufficient.

It is important to note that if midsurface modeling was applied during preprocessing, the roof panel thickness must also be accounted for when defining this clearance. Subsequently, the velocity calculated (as shown below) was assigned as the initial velocity of the mass.

$$m * g * h = \frac{1}{2} * m * v^2 \tag{1}$$

$$V = \sqrt{2 * g * h} \tag{2}$$

Where m is the mass of the falling object, g is the gravity, h is the object height determined by the standard, and V is the velocity of the falling object.

Figure 8 presents the operator cabin in its test-ready configuration for the FOPS analysis, along with the defined fixation regions and the impact mass location. For the sake of computational efficiency and faster solution times, only the critical portion of the operator cabin required for analysis was modeled and utilized.

Figure 8: Boundary conditions

2.2. Results

Upon completion of the case, displacement fields and stress distributions were evaluated. The finite element analysis (FEA) results were subsequently compared with the corresponding physical test outcomes. The primary objective of the FEA was to minimize the overall cost of physical testing by reducing the required number of test iterations. A strong correlation was observed between the numerical predictions and the experimental measurements, demonstrating the reliability of the computational model. The comparative results of the analysis and testing are presented in Figures 9 and 10, while the sequential time-step progression of the analysis is illustrated in Figure 11.

Figure 9: Analysis deformation

Figure 10: Test deformation

Figure 11: Analysis time steps

As a result, the analyzed model did not exhibit any contact with the Deflection-Limiting Volume (DLV). Therefore, the FOPS system of the HİDROMEK construction machine is confirmed to be in full compliance with the relevant standard.

3. Conclusions

In this study, the FOPS system of a HİDROMEK construction machine was evaluated using computer-aided structural analysis methods. The numerical results were compared with corresponding physical test data, and a strong correlation was observed between the two. Consequently, employing finite element analysis for FOPS evaluation proves to be an effective approach for reducing both the number of required physical tests and the associated costs.

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